

Digital Technologies: Vocabulary Development Instructions For Reading Comprehension

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Abstract. This study explored the challenges of English teachers in using digital technologies to deliver vocabulary lessons to students. This study employed a phenomenological research design which aims to determine the experiences and perceptions of the eight (8) participants. The emerging themes on the challenges of English language teachers in developing the vocabulary of students in using digital technologies were digital transformation trend, facilitating digital-based collaborative learning activities, and teacher digital readiness. The emerging themes on the teachers coping ways with the challenges of developing the vocabulary of students using digital technologies were taking advantage of user-friendly interface, contextualizing digital resources, and willing to constantly learn. Lastly, on the educational management insights the themes drawn from the experience of the teachers were interactive collaboration improves gains in vocabulary, digital tools for students' autonomy, and digital tools for improving student word retention. The results implied for school administrators to include through SLAC or INSET the development of contextualized digital tools in the schools for the development and improvement of learning and to raise the higher academic performance of learners. Moreover, the results generated provided comprehensive data in conducting future research with similar scope.

KEY WORDS

1. Digital tools 2. vocabulary development 3. 21st century learning

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1. Introduction

Reading comprehension is a complex process that relies on multiple interrelated factors such as reader characteristics, text complexity, task demands, and contextual influences. A recent study by Hu et al., (2022) highlights how both vocabulary and grammar knowledge significantly impact reading comprehension in EFL learners, with vocabulary often playing a more critical role in facilitating meaning decoding and inferencing. Another recent investigation by Pickren et al., (2023) confirms that limited grammar proficiency can impair readers' ability to understand complex sentence structures and internal text cohesion. Reader factor includes prior knowledge, linguistic skill, and metacognitive awareness. The text factor encompasses genre, structure, and content of reading material; work factor includes aim of reading effort; and context factor involves socio-cultural environment and quality of reading instruction (Dhakal, 2024). Vocabulary is associated with all of these factors since all practices differentiate during the reading process for determining word meanings according to the reader's back-

ground knowledge, ability, metacognitive skills, and motivation. On the other hand, the text chosen according to the reading purpose will make the reader face texts that have different content and words. Nagy and Scott (2000) contend that an English language student should know 90 %-95 % word meanings in the language to be able to derive meaning from the text. Even though they argued that the correlation between comprehension and vocabulary ranges from .85 to .95, other researchers argued that vocabulary is the strongest variable associated with comprehension, so scholars require focusing on vocabulary. However, English language students have been reported to have problems with vocabulary development (Manihuruk, 2020). Research has also confirmed that the students' difficulty in English reading comprehension originated from a lack of vocabulary size and depth. This issue happened before the pandemic where instructions and remediation are given in a face-to-face manner. Sadly, the problem on English reading comprehension is becoming worse because students have to study remotely- away from their English teacher. In distance learning, assessments and remediation are currently difficult to undertake due to some problems of teachers and students such as poor internet connection, not having communication devices, and social distancing, and these result to a bigger problem in English reading comprehension. For example, in Netherland, eighty percent of teacher in the study of Goudeau et al., (2021) responded that creating a language-rich environment on Zoom has been hard for them, and that it impacted reluctant readers who do not spend enough time reading at home. In Thailand, Kasham (2021) noted that English reading gap has existed in their country long before the pandemic. With the occurrence of it, inequalities in literacy rates deepened. Students at lower-achieving schools in Thailand fell further behind, widening the pre-existing achievement gap between the rich and poor students in their country. Lack of internet connection, lack of communication devices, and lack of parents' support at home are also present in the distance learning in their educational system. These result to the difficulties of English teachers' in the conduct of reading assessment and remediation to students. In Philippines, Baltazar, et. al. (2020) reported that the pandemic has put the English language students behind the learning curve. A comparison of reading ability scores among Filipino students in high school before and after COVID-19 face-to-face classroom shutdowns showed that those who already had reading problems were up to six months behind where they should have been. Because face-to-face instruction was stopped and many students went virtually, those already struggling with their English reading skills did not get the pull-out, small group intervention when they needed it, beyond regular classroom instruction, and their English reading comprehension skills got worse over time. Therefore, reading comprehension instruction becomes more challenging for English Language teachers in this pandemic, especially in developing students' vocabulary. Although vocabulary can be taught indirectly, the time dedicated to building vocabulary should not be as significant (Rashid et al., 2022), because even one word needs to be taught several times in order for a student to memorize it and understand its usage. Teaching vocabulary to students learning remotely becomes more demanding as it requires more time and the adaption of reading remediation strategies in a digital learning environment. Undoubtedly, emerging digital technologies have brought about major changes in the teaching and learning processes (Timotheou et al., 2022). These technologies, have led to a proliferation of studies that explore their use in education. Language teaching studies and practices have also been affected from this tide of change. By providing flexible, practical, and personalized opportunities of use, digital technologies chal-

lunge the conventional ways of teaching remarkably. Especially with computers, smartphones, laptop, and tablet that come with both powerful hardware and software, learning on the go becomes more and more convenient. As Andrew (2025) highlighted, the big and touch-sensitive screen of today's computers, smartphones, laptop, and tablet offer great advantages. Vocabulary teaching is at the heart of developing reading comprehension and achieving competence in the target language. There has been constant effort in search of the best technique to teach vocabulary. Nowadays, the emergence of technology makes a sweeping change in the traditional way of learning and teaching and this was intensified when distance learning was implemented as a response to continue education despite the pandemic. Due to the positive impact of digital technologies in the process of teaching and learning English reading comprehension, as well as due to the pandemic that forced teachers

and students to quickly adapt to distance learning, applying the digital technologies properly in distance educational context can optimize the students' concern and motivation in improving vocabulary for the sake of better reading comprehension of students. However, in distance learning, English language students are required to be more responsible and required to work more independently than in face-to-face class. Unfortunately, there is little empirical research which investigates the challenges of English Language teachers in the delivery of vocabulary lessons in a distance learning setting to address the widening gap of reading comprehension caused by the pandemic. This study also explores the challenges of English teachers in using digital technologies to deliver vocabulary lessons to students. The results of the research can benefit English teachers struggling to improve their students' vocabulary to heal the pressing problem of reading comprehension.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study aimed to explore the challenges of English teachers in using digital technologies to deliver vocabulary lessons to students. In an increasingly cyber-driven world, digital learning environment has been an interesting experience for students especially that students in this generation are digital natives. Aside from being digital natives, distance learning provides students with more engagement in a digital learning environment especially that education department is working to provide students with computer and internet access at home. This presents an opportunity for English language teachers to improve

the English reading comprehension skills of students through vocabulary development with the help of digital technologies. Regardless the opportunities that digital technologies provide to English language teachers in a distance learning platform, issues or challenges exist that hampers their delivery of quality vocabulary instruction that could help elevate students reading comprehension skills. This study will dig the issues or challenges, as well as the coping strategies of English language teachers in order to generate educational management insights that will be helpful in addressing the widening gap of English reading comprehension brought by the pandemic.

1.2. Research Questions—The primary research questions of this study are the following:

- (1) What are the challenges of English language teachers in developing the vocabulary of students using digital technologies?
- (2) How do English teachers cope with the challenges of developing the vocabulary of students using digital technologies?
- (3) What educational management insights are drawn from the experiences of English lan-

guage teachers?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following terms were defined for use in this study: Digital Technologies – These are electronic tools, systems, devices and resources that generate, store or process data. Well known examples include multimedia and computers (Johnstone et al., 2022). Digital Learning – It is any type of learning that uses digital technologies (Sailer et al., 2021). Distance Learning – It is a method of study where teachers and students do not meet in a classroom but use the internet, e-mail, mail, etc., to have classes; It is when students are separated from teachers and peers. This means that students learn remotely and do not have face-to-face learning with the teacher or other students (Frael, M., 2019) Reading comprehension – It is the ability to read text, process it and understand its meaning. It relies on two, interconnected abilities: word reading (being able to decode the symbols on the page) and language comprehension (being able to understand the meaning of the words and sentences) (Sewell Main, 2022). Vocabulary – It is the body of words used in a particular language; the body of words known to an individual person.

1.4. Significant of the Study—The findings reported in this study will have important implications for educational authorities and professional practice. Specifically, for the following individuals: Policy Makers. The findings of the study would give them ideas to make curriculum in which reading comprehension strategies, such as vocabulary e-learning, would be easily adapted in an online learning platform. School Administrators. The findings of the study would give them ideas on on what skills, knowledge and resources are needed for teachers to effectively improve students' English reading comprehension schools in online learning platform. Teachers. Educational management insights formulated in this study could guide them in improving their delivery of reading comprehension teaching strategies. Teachers could benchmark best practices from the experiences of the participants and could analyze and reflect effectively the challenges they encounter in the delivery of the intervention, thus uplifting their passion and motivation in teaching. Future Researchers. The findings generated provided comprehensive data in conducting future researches with similar or relevant scope

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study is anchored on the Literacy Acquisition Theory of Gee (2015). He supports the generalization of this study. Literacy includes vocabulary. A person needs to understand the meaning of critical words they will be reading to promote comprehension and hence be able to communicate effectively. A person needs to seek literacy to build self-esteem and overall quality of life. Every person must be literate. A literate person can read, write, and speak with understanding and comprehension. Literacy continues to evolve daily, and with these constant changes, difficulties arise in the ability to acquire literacy. He defines literacy as “control of uses of language”, where discourses are a socially accepted association among ways of using language, of thinking, and of acting that can be used to identify oneself as a member of a socially meaningful group or “social network”. Literacy acquisition encompasses the person’s participation in meaningful, authentic literacy events (Butterfuss et al., 2020). One of the roots of literacy is the ability to read with comprehension. Without comprehension, a person gains no meaning from what he/she read. Comprehension strate-

gies are used to increase a person's understanding of the text to help him/her become active readers by engaging with the text. One of the comprehension strategies is developing vocabulary. Since comprehension is the ultimate goal of reading, the importance of vocabulary development cannot be underestimated. The size of a person's vocabulary predicts the ability to learn to read and gain understanding of the world. Another theory is the New Literacy and Technology Theory. Another theory that supports this study is the New Literacy and Technology Theory of Barton Hamilton (2000). According to them, literacy is a socially constructed, continuously changing process in which knowledge is informed and constructed by everyday interactions with tools that build and maintain social relations. Literacy is not simply an individual cognitive activity; it is a communicative tool for different social groups with social rules about the production of literacy for specific purposes. New Literacy and Technology theory significantly influences the ongoing evolution of literacy definitions. Prior to the New Literacy definition, reading comprehension was seen as an essential tool for learning to occur, and as a vehicle for assessing and communicating the meaning of printed texts. Learning to read words and understanding meaning were an integral part of learning to understand how the world works socially and culturally. The goal is to transform society's practices and beliefs that are more socially, economically, culturally, and politically just. Research in NLS suggests that "in practice literacy varies from one context

to another and one culture to another, and so, therefore, do the effects of the different literacies in different conditions". Fitzgerald et al. (2020) define new literacies as "new socially recognized ways of generating, communicating and negotiating meaningful content through the medium of encoded texts". New literacies imply that new technologies are continuously emerging that will require a person to read text and comprehend meaning in different ways, using other processes. Technology affects how a person communicates and disseminates information. This affects how a person acquires literacy skills. New literacies operate similarly to how traditional literacy generates, communicates, and negotiates meaning; however, new literacies use text, sound, videos, hyperlinks, and other forms of technology. What it means to be considered a literate member of society is continuously changing as new literacy technologies appear in the global world. As the global world evolves, literate members must be able to identify important information, comprehend it, gather and evaluate it, and use it to solve problems and communicate with others. The conceptual framework of the study is presented in Figure 1. Based on the figure, there are two interconnected variables. These variables are the (1) Challenges of English language teachers in developing the vocabulary of students using digital technologies; (2) English language teachers cope with the challenges of developing the vocabulary of students using digital technologies; (3) Insights drawn from the experience of English language teachers.

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the method, research participants, data collection, the role of the researcher, data analysis, the trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. The subsequent design and implementation of this study, as elaborated in this chapter, were necessitated by the exploration of facts and knowledge.

2.1. *Philosophical Assumptions—*

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

The philosophical assumption served as a framework for collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data in a specific field of study. It established the background I used for the following conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions had different types, which I elaborated below. Ontology. This part of the research pertained to how the issue related to the nature of reality. According to Pretorius (2024), reality is subjective and multiple as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addressed the nature of reality for me as a qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities existed, such as my reality, those of individuals I investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, I investigated the realities of English teachers in using digital technologies to deliver vocabulary lessons to students. In this study, I relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes, themes that reflected their words, and

provided evidence of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. I made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the results. I upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This referred to the awareness of how knowledge claims were justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Khalifa (2023) stated that on the epistemological assumption, I attempted to lessen the distance between myself and the participants. He suggested that, as a researcher, I should collaborate, spend time in the field with participants, and become an ‘insider’. This study intended to gather information from the realities of English teachers in using digital technologies to deliver vocabulary lessons to students. I followed the guidelines set by DepEd and the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF). It was

assured that there was an establishment of close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry. Axiology. It referred to the role of values in research. Boswell and Babchuk (2022) averred that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggested that I openly discuss values that shaped the narrative and include my interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. I ensured that the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants was upheld. I understood the personal and value-

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Methodology is different from method. Methodology is a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Bhosale, 2023). In this study, the lived experiences and perspectives of English teachers in using digital technologies to deliver vocabulary lessons to students were investigated, particularly those participants from Sta. Ana National High School, Division of Davao City. My drive in knowing the deeper meaning of their experiences became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means of which was considered helpful in looking for meanings and motivations that underlined cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena. By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the floating teachers in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols and meaning of the experiences were

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research design, since it focused on the lived experiences and perspectives of English teachers in us-

laden nature of information gathered from the study. Therefore, I preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpreted the answers in the light of the participants' interpretation. Rhetoric. This philosophical assumption allowed me to write in a literary, informal style, using the personal voice and employing qualitative terms and limited definitions. In the context of the study, I used the first person in the elucidation of the experiences of English teachers in using digital technologies to deliver vocabulary lessons to students.

presented. Phenomenological research is based on two premises. The first is that experience is a valid, rich and rewarding source of knowledge; this experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lay in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge, and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Englander Morley, 2021). By doing phenomenology, which concerns with the "what" and the "how" (Anero Tamayo, 2023), I projected that the subjective experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of the physical education teachers were explored, and insights were drawn as a basis for possible future research and policy analysis in relation to this research.

ing digital technologies to deliver vocabulary lessons to students. According to Dumlaog (2022), phenomenology is an approach to qualitative research that focuses on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular

group. The fundamental goal of the approach is to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with a group of individuals who had first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread and culled for phrases and themes that were grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, I was able to construct the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Lim (2024) also noted that, with roots in philosophy, psychology, and education, phenomenology attempts to extract the purest, untainted data. In some interpretations of the approach, bracketing was used to document personal experiences with the subject, helping to remove myself from the process. One method of bracketing was taking notes. According to Tenny et al. (2022), the phenomenological research design is a qualitative type of research for which interviews provided an in-depth method that could grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects' perspective. Naeem et al. (2023) also claimed that interviews are primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. Often, audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews were helpful in follow up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as to investigate their responses further. In this qualitative research, I employed interviews to explore the meanings of central themes within the subjects' world. The primary objective of conducting interviews was to understand the meaning behind what the interviewees said (CourseHero, 2020). Withal, based on the statements of Hollenbeck (2024), I transcribed and typed the data into a computer file in order to analyze it af-

ter interviewing. Interviews were beneficial for uncovering the story behind a participant's experiences and for pursuing in-depth information around a topic. I collected data, typically via extended interviews, from individuals who had experienced the phenomenon under investigation. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation that extracted significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied together to make a general description of the experience, both the textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. I incorporated my meaning of the experiences here. Finally, I wrote the report so that readers could better understand the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges were pointed out. I required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study were individuals who had experienced the phenomenon. I needed to bracket my own experiences and observations, which was challenging to do. I had to decide how and when my observations were to be incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity, and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they were a powerful tool for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study was to explore and assess the teacher experience and feelings towards the school environment and the perspectives of the English teachers, I intended to employ the phenomenology type of qualitative research method.

2.4. *Research Participants*—The participants of this study were the eight (8) teachers of Sta. Ana National High School, Division of Davao City. I chose the participants based on the following criteria: (1) they must be retireable teachers aged 55 years; (2) they must

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—The ethical considerations were significant in the design of this research study. I needed to consider several ethical issues related to the research participants in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations were one of the most important aspects of the research. I had to adhere to promote the aims of the research, impart authentic knowledge, ensure truth, and prevent error. Social Value. Research is essential to society. In this study, the social value was focused on the experience of teachers. This study was conducted explicitly among the elementary teachers. This study also served as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions where classroom teachers could benefit. Thus, the social problem that pushed my interest as a researcher was the challenges faced by teachers in the use of interactive media instruction in the classroom as a way to ameliorate teaching competence. Informed Consent. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation as cited by Xu (2020) was adhered to. I ensured that the invitation to the participants made it clear that their participation in the research was completely voluntary

2.6. *Role of the Researcher*—I had a responsibility to uncover, transfer, and exploit knowledge for the benefit of educational institutions. To do so, I took up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. I conducted the interviews with the participants and guided

have a very satisfactory rating in the new normal IPCRF; and (3) they must be teaching an English language class. I utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell Poth, 2018). It was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling.

and was based on the understanding of adequate information. The recruitment and selection of participants were documented in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was critical to conducting informed, ethical, and authentic phenomenological inquiry. As Tavakol and Sandars (2025) emphasized, building participant rapport and transparency enhanced the credibility and dependability of qualitative findings, ensuring that I faithfully represented participants' lived experiences. All participants were given an informed consent form before I scheduled the interviews and carried out the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter was to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the consent letter to me before participating.

them in the process. I interpreted ideas and responses based on existing literature and related studies, rather than relying on my knowledge, thoughts, or feelings, to avoid the intrusion of bias. Expert in Qualitative Method. I implemented the qualitative method correctly. To do so, I assessed myself and sought help from my

research adviser and other research professionals. These helped me exhibit competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews properly according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting suitable artifacts, images, and journal portions, and employing Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of Data. I ensured various methods for documenting the interview and Focus Group Discussion, including handwritten notes and audio and/or video recordings. The recordings were transcribed verbatim before data analysis began. Records I made were secured adequately as they contained sensitive information and were relevant to the research. However, as data were being collected, my primary responsibility was to safeguard the participants and their data. Mecha-

nisms for such safeguarding were clearly articulated to the participants and were approved by a relevant research ethics review board before I began the research. Analyst of Data. I viewed the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding, and theming. I made sure that the findings were accurate to the participants and that their voices were heard. Organizer and Presenter of Data. I presented the problem and the related literature and studies that supported it. I presented the study's findings by addressing each research question, presenting the results, and using themes to illustrate how the research questions were answered. Moreover, I gave future directions and implications of the study for the improvement of educational policy and practices.

2.7. Data Collection—To ensure safe educational continuity amid the challenges of COVID-19, this study adhered to the Department of Health (DOH) Administrative Order No. 2020-0015 or the Guidelines on the Risk-Based Public Health Standards for COVID-19 Mitigation, cited by the IATF to aid all sectors in all settings in implementing non-pharmaceutical interventions. The following was the step-by-step process I followed in gathering the needed data: Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. I asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. I sent a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent, accompanied by Chapters 1 and 2, along with the research instrument. This letter explained the study's objectives and identified the participants. I waited for the response of the SDS before conducting the study. Asking permission from the school heads. After securing the approval of the SDS, I sent letters to the principals of the schools explaining that a study would be

conducted in their school. Obtaining consent from the participants. I asked permission from the participants and their parents/guardians. I formally oriented them about the study and the process they would go through as participants. Conducting the interview. I conducted the in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. I took the profile of the participants, jotted down notes, and recorded the conversations using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. I carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. Transcribing the responses of the interviewees. I transcribed the responses of the interviewees precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, I translated it into English. Data coding and thematizing. After the transcription, I categorized and coded the data. Then, I extracted themes and compared and contrasted the individual data from the participants. I then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and

input from the participants. Additional information gathered was thoroughly examined and integrated into the existing body of data. After

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, I utilized thematic analysis to analyze the gathered data. I analyzed the participants' answers from the interviews using Creswell's Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell and Poth (2018), themes in qualitative research were similar codes aggregated together to form a significant idea in the database. Familiarization with the data was a common step in all forms of qualitative analysis. I immersed myself in the data, becoming intimately familiar with it by reading and re-reading the data and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding, which was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis, involved generating pithy labels for important features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding was not simply a method of data reduction; it was also an analytic process, so codes captured both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. I coded every data item and

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The framework analysis of this research was flexible, allowing me to either collect all the data and then analyze it or conduct data analysis during the collection process. I sifted, charted, and sorted the gathered data during the analysis stage under key issues and themes. This involved a five-step process: (1) familiarization, (2) identifying a thematic framework, (3) indexing, (4) charting, and (5) mapping and interpretation (Klingberg, Stalmeijer, Varpio, 2024). The framework analysis process begins with familiarization, where the researcher thoroughly immerses themselves in the data to gain an in-depth understanding of its content and nuances. This step is cru-

that, I compared and contrasted data between the participants in order to identify patterns and trends.

ended this phase by collating all my codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes meant identifying coherent and meaningful patterns in the data relevant to the research question. I ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. In reviewing themes, I reflected on whether the themes told a convincing and compelling story about the data, and I began to define the nature of each theme and the relationship between them. In defining and naming themes, I prepared a detailed analysis of each theme, identifying the 'essence' of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy, and informative name for each. Writing up involved weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data, contextualizing it in relation to existing literature. I ensured that the lived experiences and perspectives of English teachers in using digital technologies to deliver vocabulary lessons to students were presented comprehensively.

cial for grasping the overall context and identifying initial impressions. Next, developing a thematic framework involves creating a structured approach to organize and categorize the data. This framework is informed by the research questions and the insights gained during the familiarization process, serving as a guide for systematic analysis and interpretation. The third step, indexing, involves applying the thematic framework to the data. This entails coding or tagging portions of the data according to the established categories, which facilitates the efficient retrieval and comparison of relevant information. Following indexing, charting involves summarizing the coded data into visual

or tabular formats. This step helps in distilling complex information into more manageable and interpretable forms, allowing for easier examination of patterns and relationships. Finally, mapping and interpretation involve analyzing these charts to identify overarching themes, patterns, and insights. This stage is critical for

drawing meaningful conclusions, understanding relationships within the data, and answering the research questions. Throughout these steps, discussion plays a vital role in ensuring that interpretations are well-grounded, reflexive, and comprehensive, ultimately leading to a nuanced understanding of the research data.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The concepts of validity and reliability were relatively foreign to qualitative research. Instead of focusing on reliability and validity, I substituted them with data trustworthiness. Trustworthiness consisted of the following components: credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Ahmed, 2024). Credibility involved establishing that the findings of the research were credible or believable from the perspective of the participants. By observing the attributes of prolonged engagement, I contributed to a belief in the trustworthiness of the data. To address the issue of credibility, I interviewed as many research participants as possible, up to the point of saturation. Meanwhile, transferabil-

ity referred to the degree to which the findings could be generalized or transferred to other contexts. I addressed this by doing a thorough job of describing the research context and assumptions that were relevant. On the other hand, dependability refers to the consistency and repeatability of the research. I ensured that the study's findings were evaluated by the participants and scrutinized by an external reviewer. Lastly, conformability referred to the degree to which findings could be confirmed or corroborated by other researchers. Throughout the entire research process, I documented the procedures and rechecked the data to ensure accuracy. Additionally, I ensured that the findings were free from bias.

3. Results and Discussion

In this chapter, the results of the study are presented and discussed concerning the aim of the study. Moreover, the themes that emerged from the data gathered were discussed in this chapter. The results present the description and background of the participants who are assigned pseudonyms to conceal their identity. English is the international language that is used by many people all over the world to communicate among nations, either in spoken or written form. This is the reason why the curriculum in the English language was included in many educational systems in the world. In the teaching of the English language, the four language skills, namely listening, speaking, reading, and writing, should be well taught to the students. Developing the English vocabulary of the students is a significant way to enable students to master the four language skills mentioned earlier. Many strategies have already been laid down to teach the English language to students. One of the strategies is using digital technology, which is believed to stimulate the learning process by enabling teachers to produce a very productive classroom activity. However, this kind of strategy posed challenges to English teachers. Subthemes were generated to analyze the challenges they encountered effectively. Discussions on their coping strategies and insights were also presented in subthemes better to utilize them in the improvement of the English Curriculum.

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study)

3.1. Challenges of English Language Teachers in Developing the Vocabulary of Students in using Digital Technologies—Advancements in technologies in globalization enable digital technology to aid students in vocabulary learning. Digital technology has aided vocabulary acquisition through internet communication. It is often known as programs, websites, or online resources that present the lesson to students in exciting ways. However, there are English teachers who encounter challenges in using digital technology for vocabulary acquisition. Challenges encountered by the teachers should not be taken for granted. Instead, it should be studied to effectively assist English language teachers in the delivery of the lesson. Subthemes of the challenges are presented below.

3.1.1. Digital transformation trend—The digital transformation trend includes the updating and upgrading of software and programs, which fundamentally affect how users operate them. Transformation occurs as individual needs and wants change, prompting business organizations to adapt their software and programs accordingly. The participants of the study discussed that they face challenges in developing the vocabulary of students using digital technology because of such transformations.

3.1.2. Facilitating digital-based collaborative learning activities—Students' needs are evolving. 21st century students found collaboration with others more useful, relevant, and significant. Digital technology offers good communication tools that enable students to communicate with their peers, whenever and wherever they are, that is why English Language teachers use it for group works and projects. However, English Language teachers reported some challenges with regards to leading digital-based collaborative learning activities. In general, the participants' discussion on the challenges of facilitating digital-based collaborative learning activities are related to the statement of

Vali (2023) that there are some delays in digital-based collaboration in class because there are tendencies that video is lagging and downloads of learning materials are taking forever. This creates disruptions in the learning process of the students. Disruption then could lessen student engagement in the learning activity. The author reminded teachers to be innovative, creative, and adjust the learning experience for students. Further, Sathyaseelan et al. (2025) explained that digital-based group work for vocabulary development can be complicated because of its asynchronous characteristics and lack of physical presence, and its requirements for skills in handling technology, human relationships, and content-related tasks. Although there are some setbacks, the author still recommends using digital tools to improve students' vocabulary, as they can assist in communication with others, thereby increasing vocabulary. The author reminded teachers to assess the digital capability of students, including the availability of digital tools and their knowledge and skills in using them.

3.1.3. Teacher digital readiness—Teachers' ability to direct themselves in teaching and utilize digital technology in vocabulary development can significantly impact student learning effectiveness. In order to interact effectively in digital-based learning, English Language teachers must be technologically ready. This readiness is the teachers' ability to solve tasks with the use of tools and methods of ICT, namely: to perform informational activity for collecting, analyzing and storing the informational resource in order to automatize the processes of informational-methodic support; to create, evaluate and actualize the capacities of electronic educational resources and educationally-oriented informational content in the internet; or organize web interaction (communication) between educational process subjects and interactive services, which function based on tools. It is evident from the responses that teachers' readiness

Fig. 3. Emerging themes on the Challenges of English Language Teachers in developing the Vocabulary of Students in using Digital Technologies affects the learning of the students. If the teachers' readiness in teaching is highly effective, the learning process will be highly effective, and of course, this will have an impact on student learning achievement. Indeed, readiness is a must to create a change in behavior and processes. Such changes bring desirable academic outcomes. In essence, the teacher can actively engage students in the learning process and take personal responsibility for the learned information. In general, the discussion of the participants coincides with the statement of Yohana et al. (2020) that the teacher has the task to encourage, guide, and provide learning experiences for students to achieve learning goals. The teacher has the responsibility to observe all class activities to support the development process of students. However, this would be done by the teachers only if they have sufficient readiness for their lesson. The more ready the teacher is, the more focused she is, and the more students learn. Another study that coincides with the statements of the participant is the statement of Kalam (2021). According to her, readiness is a qualitative, intrinsic representation of teacher behavior that is very meaningful. From the above understanding, the author further explained that the teacher's readiness carries out a teaching action. A teacher must have the readiness to teach because this is closely related to the results that the students will achieve. The learning process and student learning outcomes are not only determined by the structure, pattern, and curriculum content. However, they are also determined by the competence of teachers who teach and guide them. The author emphasized that the teacher plays a crucial role, being responsible for the success or failure of the teaching and learning process.

3.2. *Teachers' Coping Ways with the Challenges of Developing the Vocabulary of Students using Digital Technologies*—To become a proficient English language user, one must possess a variety of qualities, and one of the important aspects is a wide range of vocabulary. Sun et al. (2023), vocabularies consist of 5,000 to 8,000 word families. It is challenging for learners with a limited vocabulary level to understand the texts and acquire words incidentally as native speakers. Many students recognize the importance of vocabulary in learning English as a second language (L2), but they struggle to acquire words due to various factors, particularly the complexity of the English language, which operates on a different linguistic system from their native language.

3.2.1. *Taking advantage of a user-friendly interface*—Using technology for education provokes students' curiosity, boosts their engagement, and leads to better learning, increases vocabulary, and improves reading comprehension. These factors are a priority for every effective teacher, and today they can be easily achieved by using digital tools in the classroom. The participants shared that in utilizing digital tools, it is necessary to use applications or software that are user-friendly. They coined the term that these are technical solutions that are easy for all to manipulate. Choosing these tools will not frustrate students during access, and thus improve their interest in learning. The ease of use of a website or software describes that the user can operate the technical system easily and intuitively. The navigation through the program should, of course, be structured. In short, the easier and faster the user understands the application, the more user-friendly it is. Poor usability leads to negative user experiences, so this website/software will likely be avoided in the future. On the other hand, good usability refines learning acquisition, improves reading skills and increases academic growth (Reviso, 2019). Since vocabulary acquisition is consid-

ered to be an essential part of language learning, vocabulary mobile learning applications (apps) have become a popular form of mobile-assisted language learning. Research has shown that a mobile application designed and based on students' needs and continuously facilitated by a teacher is effective in the enhancement of students' performance and contributes to positive learning outcomes (Klímová, 2019). Despite an increasing number of mobile learning applications offering a powerful learning environment, it is certain that the traditional methods of learning foreign languages are still useful. However, they need to be updated, combined with new trends, and adapted to the needs and skills of the students (Mikulecký, 2019).

3.2.2. *Contextualizing digital resources*—Supplementary Learning Materials are substantial tools for delivering lessons of teachers to the learners. Teachers are the best developers of these supplementary learning materials. They have the best capacity to develop a set of well-fit instructional materials for the learners to attain mastery of learning competencies. Contextualized instructional materials or supplementary learning materials through the use of digital tools enable the learners to pave the way of acquiring vocabulary skills which are very essential for reading comprehension. As far as instruction is concerned, teachers should deliver the lesson well and try and encourage the learners to discover learning from themselves through the help of contextualized learning resources. This is a skill intended for the 21st-century learners that teachers need to master to make them a well-qualified educator. Thus, teachers should translate information to the learners in the most appropriate and suited way based on the learners' state of understanding. It is evitable that the curriculum as well should be contextualized to promote mastery of learning competencies (Jimenes, 2020). Contextualization is designed to seamlessly link the students' acquired knowledge and skills to concrete appli-

cations in context to their lives and interest. In this way, they develop not only the content but also the procedural knowledge and metacognitive awareness of when and how to apply what has been learned. This approach builds a learning community within the classroom and values knowledge and skills within the social context. Through contextualization, context and culture take place. Thus, the more novel material is contextualized, the more the students see its importance and utility, there is greater motivation to learn it (Rivera Sanchez, 2020).

3.2.3. Willing to Constantly Learn—Online distance learning adheres to the use of technology. The participants are continuously familiarizing themselves with different digital tools to use in improving vocabulary skills. To equip themselves with the new normal education, the participants attend webinar sessions, watch video tutorials, and are mentored by peers. Constant learning widens teachers' knowledge and develops useful skills as they design their instructional plans this is in relation to the culture of antifragility, Digital Technology, Digital Pedagogy 4.0, Technological Capability that was mentioned by (Grandeza, 2024) . Constant learning provides growth and development of teachers as professionals, making them ready and prepared in embracing changes in the teaching landscape. Teachers play a significant role in improving the quality of education; hence, capacity building of teachers must receive top priority. Today's teaching careers look nothing like they did 20 or even just 10 years ago. Like technology, the field of education evolves

3.3. Educational Management Insights Drawn From the Experience of the Teachers—The participants shared their educational management insights, and it was narrowed down into one to generate the themes. These themes were carefully analyzed and formulated based on what came from participants' accounts and

so fast that techniques, skills and technologies become obsolete within five to 10 years. That is why being a lifelong learner plays an important role in the educational process. It helps educators incorporate new tools and strategies into the learning process to boost their students' learning development. Lifelong learning is an essential challenge for inventing the future of societies; it is a necessity rather than a luxury to be considered. It is a mindset and a habit for people to acquire (Mezza, 2022). Educators who are lifelong learners are more successful. They can conquer challenges. People with a lifelong learning mindset treat mistakes and challenges as part of the learning process. They do not see mistakes as failures. Mistakes provide them with new information that they can use as they continue to find ways to solve a problem or challenge. Educators never know what types of questions students will ask. Lifelong learners make learning a regular habit to adapt to changes and student actions. By embracing a student-like mindset and learning to turn self-education into a daily habit, teachers can hone their current skills and develop new ones while enriching their minds. Then, when the time to adapt arrives, the transitions are less bumpy (ClassIn, 2023). The framework below summarizes teachers' coping strategies with the challenges of developing students' vocabulary using digital technologies. Based on the figure 4, three themes emerged from the participants' responses: taking advantage of user-friendly interfaces, contextualizing digital resources, and being willing to learn constantly.

reflections. The subthemes are shown below:

3.3.1. Interactive collaboration improves gains in vocabulary—Digital technologies offer numerous platforms for students to produce a successful collaboration. Some examples of digital tools that the students can use to simplify collaboration are using social media and

Fig. 4. Emerging themes on the Teachers Coping ways with the Challenges of Developing the Vocabulary of Students using Digital Technologies

Google Docs. These digital tools are interactive in a way that they implement text, images, audio, and video using communication tools that allows a person to interact with other. In general, the responses of the participants relates with the study of Arrifin (2021). The author claimed that collaborative learning triggers interaction and meaningful word vocabulary development, which spark positive learners' attitudes towards learning new words. What is more is that, through the creation of shared meaning, and in the exchange of information, knowledge and expertise amongst group members, collaborative environments form empowering social contexts that are by personal relationships, preferences, and motivations. Teachers can expect that the personal relationships that develop vocabulary skills help to establish lasting motivation in learning the language. Moreover, the study of Arrifin (2021) verifies the responses of the participants. The author found out in his study that learning in an individual environment cannot be as effective as learning in a collaborative learning environment. Data from his study showed that the difference in growth in vocabulary knowledge was statistically significant, because the collaborative group showed a significantly higher amount of growth in vocabulary knowledge compared to the individual group. Working together in a collaborative environment and creating an interactive process in the vocabulary learning can cause better understanding of words among the students.

3.3.2. *Digital tools for students' autonomy*—Students' autonomy is when they take control and responsibility for their learning, both in terms of what they learn and how they learn it. It takes as its starting point the idea that students are capable of self-direction and can develop an independent, proactive approach to their studies. The participants asserted that students can control their learning process as much as possible and can become quite independent of teachers when they work with digital tools.

For this reason, the participants imply that using technology in learning vocabulary in the 21st century is highly needed. Since students today are 21st-century students or digital natives, as they possess high technology, bringing digital technology into the classroom will meet their needs and increase their motivation, especially in learning a language. Indeed, digital tools play a significant role in fostering student learning autonomy, as discussed by the participants. Consequently, they shared recommendations on developing students' digital literacy to enable them to utilize digital tools to their full potential. The focus of the recommendations from the participants is on character building through the use of digital tools. Technology is fluid and constantly changing and improving. This means that students must possess good characteristics, such as patience, perseverance, and determination, to be adaptive to the changes, as well as to the problems they might encounter while using the tools. Students who use digital tools for learning should not give up; they should be ready for every situation and continue learning despite the roadblocks.

3.3.3. *Digital tools for improving student word retention*—Digital learning platform offers various features and tools that prevent cognitive overload among students, where the brain is forced to digest bulk information. Digital tools apply micro-learning to its lesson and learning management. The participants of the study shared insights regarding this. The participants argue that the key to fostering a digital mindset in students lies in the emphasis on critical thinking. Critical thinking has always been emphasized in literacy skills, but it becomes much more apparent when it comes to interpreting digital content. The author agrees with the participants that students have to learn critical thinking skills. There is no real correlation between how well a student interprets information on paper and how well a student can interpret in a digital environment, according to Bahri et al. (2024).

Therefore, teachers must teach those skills and strategies to ensure the digital literacy of their students. In general, the responses of the participants can be verified through the study of Tulgar (2021). The author experimented with putting a personal digital assistant (PDA)-based English vocabulary learning system to help participants develop vocabulary at their own learning pace. The results showed that the method attracted students' attention and improved their vocabulary output due to the versatile and efficient learning environment offered by PDAs. The findings also showed that using such digital technology to learn vocabulary made learning more enjoyable, and words learned through it were easier to recall. Further, the responses could be verified in the study of Hidayat et al. (2025). The author compared the performance of students in paper-based vocabulary learning (flashcards) to digital vocabulary learning. Two groups of students were used. He found out that there was a statistically significant difference between the

two groups. Students learning through digital tools outscored students learning through the traditional way. Therefore, students using digital technologies to learn vocabulary were more successful and had more positive attitudes towards learning than those using paper-based materials. Digital tools offer more knowledge retention than paper-based materials. Based on the figure above, three themes emerged from the responses of the participants in the educational management insights drawn from their experiences. These interactive collaborations enhance vocabulary gains, promote student autonomy through digital tools, and improve word retention. The themes suggest that digital tools empower teachers to tailor learning experiences for students, either collaboratively or independently. Such improvements in instructional methods and customized learning experiences increase the knowledge retention of the students. Thus, it develops student productivity and efficiency in learning the language.

4. Implications and Future Directions

Presented in this chapter is a brief overview of the study, followed by implications based on the findings of the study. Future directions in the field of teachers' experiences were also discussed here.

4.1. Findings—The results of the study reflect key principles from the Literacy Acquisition Theory, which suggests that students develop vocabulary and literacy skills more effectively when they are exposed to real and meaningful use of language in context. The use of digital tools to support vocabulary instruction allows for engaging and authentic learning experiences that can help strengthen students' language development. In line with this, the New Literacy and Technology Theory views literacy as a dynamic concept shaped by technological advancements. This theory highlights the importance of integrating digital tools in education to support modern forms of commu-

nication and learning. The emerging themes in the study, such as digital transformation, collaborative learning through digital platforms, and teacher readiness, demonstrate the need for teachers to embrace evolving technology to support students' vocabulary growth better. While obstacles such as unequal access to devices and the need for further teacher training exist, the study shows that educators are motivated to improve their digital skills to enhance teaching and meet students' learning needs in a digital age.

4.2. Implications—The emerging themes on teachers' coping ways with the challenges of developing students' vocabulary using digital technologies were taking advantage of user-

Fig. 5. Emerging Themes on Educational Management Insights Drawn from the Experience of the Teachers

friendly interfaces, contextualizing digital resources, and being willing to learn constantly. These themes implied that digital tools give educators access to resources that allow more flexibility regarding content selection and layout of the text, as well as the means to modify content based on the particular needs of students and local communities. The use of ancillary materials such as source documents and alternative multimedia presentations of information has helped compensate for struggling readers' limitations in background knowledge. It has enriched learning opportunities for all readers. Furthermore, emerging themes in educational management insights from teachers' experiences include interactive collaboration, enhancing vocabulary gains, and the use of digital tools for student autonomy and improved word retention. The themes suggest that digital tools empower teachers to tailor learning experiences for students, either collaboratively or independently. Such improvements in instructional methods and customized learning experiences increase the knowledge retention of the students. Thus, it develops student productivity and efficiency in learning the language.

4.3. *Future Directions*—This research provides significant empirical, theoretical, and practical contributions to investigate English teachers' experiences in using digital technologies to deliver vocabulary lessons to students. The data obtained had directions for various stakeholders in education, including policymakers, administrators, and teachers. The future directions of this study are as follows: For policymakers to synergize better with school leaders and teachers in creating policies and investing in e-reading technology, they must attend carefully to the technology's evidence base, provide the infrastructure the technology requires, and take maximum advantage of the increased efficiency and volume of information that technology offers. For school administrators to in-

clude, through SLAC or INSET, the development of contextualized electronic media in the schools for the development and improvement of learning, and to raise the academic performance of learners. They may tap the potential of school ICT Coordinators, Illustrators, and Layout Artists with the assistance of School LR Coordinators who are capacitated in the latest software applications to promote collaboration of interactive multimedia materials in promoting reading level through improved vocabulary acquisition. For teachers to be equipped with ample knowledge to conduct teaching and learning using digital tools efficiently. Moreover, teachers must consider the students' social, economic, and family backgrounds, as some students may have limitations in owning and utilizing mobile phones at home. For future researchers, it is recommended to consider the involvement of participants from a wide range. As a suggestion, future research should involve a wide range of participants consisting of students from a diverse range of ages, English proficiency levels, and experience in using digital tools in language learning. By involving a wider range of participants, the study could be more significant since it consists of a lot of variables to work with. The acceptance of students can be viewed from various perspectives, including their age, English proficiency level, and experience with digital tools in language learning. In addition, future research could benefit from employing more learning digital tools. In this way, a greater variety and in-depth information regarding the preferred features could be collected, and researchers could gain more insight into the challenges faced by students in using digital tools in learning vocabulary. Future studies could also employ experimental research to see whether the use of digital tools in learning vocabulary is effective for the students or otherwise.

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